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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AARON RENY Bearing USN 5SU21PT001 has completed his/her mini project on
“Anatomy Model Making” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ABDUL JABBAR K Bearing USN 5SU21PT002 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ABHINENDHU G S Bearing USN 5SU21PT003 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ABHIRAM V K Bearing USN 5SU21PT004 has completed his/her mini project on
“**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ADIL ROSHAN K Bearing USN 5SU21PT005 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AFEEDA BAIJU Bearing USN 5SU21PT006 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AFEEFAH ABDUL KHADAR Bearing USN 5SU21PT007 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AFRAZ ASHRAF Bearing USN 5SU21PT008 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AJITH K S Bearing USN 5SU21PT009 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANANYA Bearing USN 5SU21PT010 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANANYA Bearing USN 5SU21PT011 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANJALY K K Bearing USN 5SU21PT012 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANUSHA Bearing USN 5SU21PT013 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. APARNA T R Bearing USN 5SU21PT014 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ARJUN ASHOK Bearing USN 5SU21PT015 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ARTHANA SURESH K V Bearing USN 5SU21PT016 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ARYA O Bearing USN 5SU21PT017 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ARYA PARVATHY P Bearing USN 5SU21PT018 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ASWIN SANTHOSH Bearing USN 5SU21PT019 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ATHULYA PANOLI Bearing USN 5SU21PT020 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AVANI A K Bearing USN 5SU21PT021 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AYSHA NAJEEB Bearing USN 5SU21PT022 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. B PRATHEEK PAI Bearing USN 5SU21PT023 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BHATATE VINAY MAHESH Bearing USN 5SU21PT024 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHAITHRA P M Bearing USN 5SU21PT025 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DHRUVE V S Bearing USN 5SU21PT026 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DILNA FEMI K Bearing USN 5SU21PT027 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIHA ISRA K P Bearing USN 5SU21PT028 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIMA NAJA Bearing USN 5SU21PT029 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIMA NISHA Bearing USN 5SU21PT030 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIMATHU HASRA M K P Bearing USN 5SU21PT031 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FELNA A K Bearing USN 5SU21PT032 has completed his/her mini project on
“**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HAFEEZA FATHIMA Bearing USN 5SU21PT033 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HASHIM ABOOBACKER Bearing USN 5SU21PT034 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HIBA NAZIR Bearing USN 5SU21PT035 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HUDHA GAFOOR Bearing USN 5SU21PT036 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HUSSAIN RAHIM Bearing USN 5SU21PT037 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. IBRAHIM JUNAID Bearing USN 5SU21PT038 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JADHAV ABHIJIT SANJAY Bearing USN 5SU21PT039 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JIDIN PARAMEKATTIL BHASY Bearing USN 5SU21PT040 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. K M MIDLAJ Bearing USN 5SU21PT041 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KADEEJA A Bearing USN 5SU21PT042 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KADIJATHUL ESHANA Bearing USN 5SU21PT043 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KARUNYA Bearing USN 5SU21PT044 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. LEKSHMI T Bearing USN 5SU21PT045 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. M CHAITHANYA Bearing USN 5SU21PT046 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MARIYAM SAFA Bearing USN 5SU21PT047 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MASHHOORA V Bearing USN 5SU21PT048 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MEENAKSHI PRADEEP Bearing USN 5SU21PT049 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MINHA K Bearing USN 5SU21PT050 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOHAMMAD HASHIM K A Bearing USN 5SU21PT051 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOHAMMED ABSHAR L Bearing USN 5SU21PT052 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOHAMMED AMEER SUHAIL Bearing USN 5SU21PT053 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOHAMMED ARSHAD K Bearing USN 5SU21PT054 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOHAMMED MUZAMMIL Bearing USN 5SU21PT055 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOHAMMED SHAMIL M T P Bearing USN 5SU21PT056 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUFEEDA THASNI Bearing USN 5SU21PT057 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUFEETHA M V Bearing USN 5SU21PT058 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHAMMAD SHA S Bearing USN 5SU21PT059 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHAMMAD SHAMIL T Bearing USN 5SU21PT060 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHAMMED ARIF K A Bearing USN 5SU21PT061 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHAMMED RAHIF C Bearing USN 5SU21PT062 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NAJI MUHAMMED Bearing USN 5SU21PT063 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NANDANA P S Bearing USN 5SU21PT064 has completed his/her mini project on
“Anatomy Model Making” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NANDHANA V S Bearing USN 5SU21PT065 has completed his/her mini project on
“Anatomy Model Making” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NEHA Bearing USN 5SU21PT066 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NIDEESHA ALVA Bearing USN 5SU21PT067 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NIDHI M S Bearing USN 5SU21PT068 has completed his/her mini project on
“**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PAKRUDDEEN AHMED MIDLAJ Bearing USN 5SU21PT069 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PARINITHA M NAIK Bearing USN 5SU21PT070 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. POOJARY NEHA YOGESH Bearing USN 5SU21PT071 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PRATHYUL GHOSH C Bearing USN 5SU21PT072 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RIYA FATHIMA Bearing USN 5SU21PT073 has completed his/her mini project on
“**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RIYA SANTHOSH Bearing USN 5SU21PT074 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ROOSA FIDHA Bearing USN 5SU21PT075 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. S R POOVARASI Bearing USN 5SU21PT076 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SAHANA K S Bearing USN 5SU21PT077 has completed his/her mini project on
“**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SANDRA SATHAR Bearing USN 5SU21PT078 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SANDWANA MANIKUTTAN Bearing USN 5SU21PT079 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SANGEETH KRISHNA K S Bearing USN 5SU21PT080 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SANJANA A Bearing USN 5SU21PT081 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHAIKH TASMIYA NASIR Bearing USN 5SU21PT082 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHAMIL HASHIQ Bearing USN 5SU21PT083 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHAMLA A U Bearing USN 5SU21PT084 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHASHANK K Bearing USN 5SU21PT085 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHEHREBANO BOHRA Bearing USN 5SU21PT086 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHIBINA V Bearing USN 5SU21PT087 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHIMNA K N Bearing USN 5SU21PT088 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHREE VIDYA Bearing USN 5SU21PT089 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHREYA B Bearing USN 5SU21PT090 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SIDAN K C Bearing USN 5SU21PT091 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SNEHA K V Bearing USN 5SU21PT092 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. VARSHA K P Bearing USN 5SU21PT093 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. VISMAYA N Bearing USN 5SU21PT094 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. VISMAYA P Bearing USN 5SU21PT095 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ZAINABA RABEEHA Bearing USN 5SU21PT096 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ROSHAN P R Bearing USN 5SU21PT097 has completed his/her mini project on
“**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AHAMMAD MUKTHAR Bearing USN 5SU21PT098 has completed his/her mini project on “**Anatomy Model Making**” in the second semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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